

Draping with Up-cycled Fabrics: A Creative way towards Sustainability

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ABSTRACT

The fashion sector ranks top along other industries, all over the world. In fashion industries the techniques used to make clothing produces millions of tons of garbage each year. About 85% of the fabric used in making garments, and the remaining 15% is wasted and left on the cutting room floor. Fashion industry has an impact on both the environment and the millions of people daily work in it. In this paper, a solution is proposed for applying leftover scraps of fabric to clothing in the field of draping. In order to reduce waste, modifying the manufacturing processes is the greatest challenge for zero-waste fashion. Strategies with a focus on results draw attention how fabric waste is used to create clothing and also discuss the effect of zero waste on fashion industry. The purpose of this research is to investigate the influences of sustainability in zero-waste. In this research the researcher reusing of scraps of cloth and yarns, and Tessellation etc. This study's methodology was based on primary and secondary data collection. This study implements the Zero waste fashion design approach in the field of draping for creating a unique garments design.

1. Introduction

In the clothing industry, making textiles and throwing away textile waste can harm the environment. There is a way to solve this problem: it's called zero waste draping. This means using different draping techniques to prevent fabric waste and be more creative with the fabric we have. By doing this, we can

reduce the negative impact on the environment. The purpose of this chapter is to help you better understanding zero waste draping methods. The researcher of this study wants to find out the different ways people use zero waste draping techniques to make clothes without wasting any fabric. By identifying these approaches, they hope to create garments that don't produce any waste (**Ellen McKinney, Sunhyung Cho, Ling Zhang, Rachel Eike, Eulanda Sanders**).

Fashion plays a crucial role in our lives as it encompasses social, economic, and environmental dimensions. As a material form of expression, fashion apparel holds immense significance for our personal and social relationships, influencing how we perceive ourselves and our place in society. Our clothing choices can convey a wide range of messages about our identities, values, and aspirations, serving as a means of communication and self-expression (**Shannon McGrath, 2012**). The fashion industry is currently utilizing resources in an inefficient manner due to the way in which garments are being produced. The general process of creating a garment involves several distinct stages, namely design, pattern making, construction, and production. However, the hierarchical nature of these stages has led to the development of a cut and sew fashion system, which results in an average of only 85% effective textile utilization, with the remaining 15% being discarded as off-cuts. This term refers to the leftover fabric scraps that accumulate during the manufacturing process and can account for anywhere between 10-20% of fabric waste, depending on the design of the garment (**Pragya Sharma, 2021**). Sustainability in fashion is the entire lifecycle of a garment, from its creation to its disposal, and the impact that each stage has on the environment. This includes the sourcing and production of raw materials, the manufacturing and transportation of clothing, the way garments are used and cared for by consumers, and the disposal or recycling of garments at the end of its lifespan (**Sooyoen Shim, Jisoo Kim, Youngjoo Na, 2018**). Zero waste fashion is an approach to clothing production that aims to reduce or eliminate that amount of fabric waste generated during that manufacturing process. This sustainable fashion movement is becoming increasingly popular as people seek ways to reduce their environmental impact and promote an eco-friendly way of living. There are two main methods of zero-waste fashion: pre-consumer and post-consumer. Pre-consumer zero waste fashion focuses on reducing waste during the manufacturing process itself. This can involve careful planning of the pattern layout to ensure that the fabric is used as efficiently as possible, as well as using innovative techniques such as interlocking puzzle-like pieces or using leftover fabric for embellishments, bias tape, and other design elements. Post-consumer zero-waste fashion, on the other hand, involves using existing garments or textiles to create new clothing items. This can involve up-cycling second-hand clothing or repurposing other fabrics that would otherwise go to waste (**Moni Jafar Pingki, Md. Shamshad Hasnine, Iftekhar Rahman, 2017**).

Zero-waste fashion design is when clothes are designed in a way that prevents waste during the cutting and sewing process. Normally, 15-25% of fabric is wasted during the production of clothes. The industry usually focuses on reducing waste during marker making, but this article suggests using 3D software during the design process to further reduce waste. However, the industry mostly uses 3D software as a marketing and visualization tool (**HollyMcQuillan, 2020**).

Aim-

This research focuses on the creation of unique designs using waste fabric pieces through various draping techniques. The aim is to demonstrate the designs by employing draping, by which we can effectively utilize all fabric, eliminating any notion of waste. Additionally, we propose the integration of this waste fabric draping concept into fashion design curricula to raise awareness among designers, industry persons and students about the significance of zero waste and the environmental impact of textile waste. By emphasizing the potential of draping as a means to utilize fabric remnants, we strive to eliminate the concept of waste in garment production.

Objectives-

1. To understand the importance of up-cycled fabrics
2. To explore the effect of zero waste on fashion industry.
3. To collect waste piece of fabric from tailors, boutiques and fashion houses.
4. To create unique designs by using draped waste fabric.

2. Literature Review

Riikka Kalkaja (2016) discusses that Sustainable fashion is when people try to make fashion in a way that doesn't harm the environment or people. This means that they use materials that are eco-friendly and don't create a lot of waste. When people practice sustainable fashion, they also try to buy less clothing overall and make sure that what they do buy is from ethical sources. This can mean buying second-hand clothes or choosing clothes that have been made in fair trade conditions. It can also mean choosing clothes made from organic materials, like cotton or bamboo, instead of synthetic fabrics that can harm the environment. While some people might think that sustainable fashion means only wearing boring or utilitarian clothes, there are actually many fashionable and stylish options available. By choosing sustainable fashion, people can look good and feel good about the choices they are making for the planet and the people who make our clothes.

Adil Masood Qazi, Amna Manzoor, Anika Sitara and Mudassar Abbas (2018) explained the drape clothing as drape garments, have been worn by women throughout history in many different cultures. The garments are typically made of soft, flowing fabrics that are draped or wrapped around the body in a way that creates a loose, comfortable fit. Draping, or the use of fabric to wrap and shape clothing around the body, has been a common practice in human history for thousands of years. The origin of draping can be traced back to prehistoric times, when humans began to wear animal hides and plant fibers for warmth and protection. The way draping was used in clothing also varied across cultures and social classes. The history of draped garments can be traced back to ancient times, with evidence of draped clothing being found in civilizations such as ancient Greece, Rome, Egypt, and Mesopotamia. The use of draping in clothing has continued throughout history and can be seen in various forms in modern fashion. Today, draping is used for both practical and aesthetic purposes, and designers continue to experiment with new techniques and styles.

The ancient Greeks used a lot of draping in their clothing, which means they would hang, wrap, and tie fabric around their bodies to create different styles. They would use things like pins and belts to keep the fabric in place. Greek clothing can be divided into two main types are hanging and wrapping. Two common types of draped clothing were the chiton and the peplos.

The technique is called "draping" and it involves using a piece of fabric to directly create a garment on a mannequin or a human body. Unlike traditional pattern-making methods that involve creating a paper pattern first, draping allows for the creative use of 100% of the fabric, resulting in less waste. Essentially, the fabric is draped over the form and then pinned, tucked, and manipulated until it creates the desired shape and fit. Once the draping is complete, the fabric is cut and sewn into a finished garment.

Pictures of zero waste garments create by different techniques

Geo Cut Technique

Subtraction cutting method

Jigsaw puzzle technique by the designer mark Liu

Zhanna Kutsenkova (2017) described the Sustainable fashion is a new trend in the fashion industry that focuses on being environmentally friendly and treating workers fairly. The goal is to slow down the fast-paced production and consumption of clothing in order to create a more sustainable industry that doesn't harm the environment or people. This involves reducing textile waste, using eco-friendly materials, and promoting ethical working conditions. In the literature, might come across different terms used to describe sustainable and ethical fashion, and they can sometimes be used interchangeably. For example, 'ethical fashion' can mean fashionable clothes that are made under fair working conditions, without harming the environment or workers, and using eco-friendly materials like organic cotton. Meanwhile, 'green fashion' may be used to refer to the same issues related to sustainability and ethical practices in fashion.

Pragya Sharma (2013) study on the fabric behavior and said that fabric behaves when draped, folded, or hung. This technique helps to determine the fabric's weight, texture, and drape, which are important factors in deciding how to finish the garment. By working with the fabric on the dress form, designers can gain a better sense of how the garment will fit and how it will move on the body. This allows for more informed decisions about finishing details, such as seams, hems, and closures, which can impact the overall look and feel of the final product.

Alison Gwilt (2014) described that Zero-waste fashion is a method of making clothes that aims to minimize the amount of leftover fabric that is typically thrown away during the cutting process. This approach involves designing clothing in a way that reduces or eliminates textile waste from the very beginning. Typically, around 15% of the fabric that is meant to be used for making clothes ends up as scraps on the cutting room floor. A significant amount, approximately 74%, of the textile waste that is produced is disposed of in landfills. This waste includes various types of fashion garments that can be repurposed, recycled or reused. By doing so, we can reduce the environmental impact of the textile

industry and also decrease the resources required to produce new products. Therefore, finding ways to reuse or recycle clothing can have a positive impact on both the environment and the economy.

Moni Jafar Pingki, Shamshad Hasnine, Md Iftekher Rahman (2019) said that Zero waste design is a way of clothing patterns that produce very little fabric waste. This is achieved by avoiding awkward curves and ensuring that pattern pieces fit together in a way that minimizes scraps. Designers are using different methods, substances, and technologies to make zero waste clothing that looks and feels great. This approach is becoming more popular among designers who prioritize sustainability in fashion. Zero waste fashion is a part of the larger sustainable fashion movement, which aims to reduce the environmental impact of clothing production.

Sharma, Pragya (2021) explain the idea of zero waste that has been around for a long time, although its focus has evolved over time. In the past, the primary concern was to fully utilize expensive fabrics rather than avoiding waste. Many cultures throughout history have produced clothing with minimal fabric waste, including the Greeks and Romans with their draping techniques, the Japanese with their kimonos, the Scottish with their kilts, and the Indians with their various drapes like saris, mundus, mekhalas, gamchas, and lungis. These garments often incorporated design elements like gussets, minimal arm shaping, rectangular sleeves or pants, and were engineered to match the available fabric's length and width. Even in modern Europe, the famous Parisian couturier Madeleine Vionnet incorporated zero waste in some of her creations, like a dress made out of four squares.

Lotika Gupta And Harminder Kaur Saini (2020) discuss the adoption of a Zero Waste strategy is imperative in order to eliminate inefficiencies in the use of materials, energy, and human resources, particularly in the apparel industry. It is crucial for apparel companies to accept high-quality supplies, as this enables them to achieve efficient and expedient production, while simultaneously minimizing wastage. Furthermore, it is necessary to ensure that any leftover materials after production are carefully sorted during the production process. Proper disposal of waste should also be planned to avoid any harm to the environment. It is important to note that various accessories are used during the transformation of fabric into a garment. Therefore, any garment can only be called environmentally friendly if each piece of the garment meets specific environmental requirements.

Herbal Goodness (2022) emphasized Zero-waste and said that it is a way of life that tries to reduce negative environmental effects by producing less waste. The lifestyle is strongly associated with minimalism: a way of life that tries to keep personal things to a minimum; only buys objects of essential value or that can be used for multiple purposes. It is frequently utilized to save money, space, and

personal time because fewer things mean less mess and maintenance, which means less time spent cleaning and decluttering.

3. Methodology

This study incorporates both experimental and exploratory research methods as part of its research designs. These approaches are employed to gather data effectively. The study has progressed through these phases to develop products. These stages can be described as follows:

Phase I: Exploratory Phase

Phase II: Experimental Phase

To conduct research on sustainable clothing and zero waste fabric, data was collected from various sources, including primary data obtained through market research, local study and secondary data was obtained from research papers, articles, book magazine and internet etc. The aim of this research was to utilize the waste to create sustainable clothing to satisfy their fashion needs while also being environmentally friendly.

Phase I: Exploratory Phase

In this phase we can explore the current fashion trend in sustainable clothing with zero-waste and also collected waste fabric pieces from tailors' shop, boutiques and fashion houses to create garments through different draping.

Market research/ survey: A market survey was conducted in Aligarh area, as well as online stores, to capture the current trends in sustainable clothing with a zero-waste approach. The main objective of this survey was to gain an understanding of the prevailing trends in fabric, color combinations, and embellishments used in the creation of zero-waste clothing through draping.

When designing zero-waste clothing with a sustainable approach, it is important to keep in mind the need for environmentally friendly and ethically sourced fabrics. The survey focused on identifying the fabrics that were in demand among customers, and the results indicated a strong preference for natural and organic materials like cotton, linen, hemp, and bamboo.

Collection of materials: A survey was conducted to collect the sustainable materials used in making zero waste clothing by draping.

Phase II: Experimental Phase

In this particular phase, the researcher focused on creating a garment using zero-waste principles, employing a variety of draping techniques. However, due to time constraints, the researcher was unable to produce a larger number of garments, and instead focused their efforts on developing a design.

Selection of color: The researcher chooses the colors for their designs by looking at what is currently popular on an online store and by doing market research. They use a lot of different colors in their designs based on the latest trends in order to create fashionable clothing.

Selection of material: The researcher also selects the materials as per the latest trend.

Created designs: The researcher created the unique designs that embrace the idea of zero waste. They achieved this by using draping techniques and considering the current market trends.

5. Result and Discussion

The study called " **Draping with Up-cycled Fabrics: A Creative way towards Sustainability** " aimed to understand how sustainability can be incorporated into up-cycled or zero-waste clothing and raise awareness about sustainability. They wanted to design a line of zero waste dresses for girls using sustainable design techniques. The researchers also wanted to learn about people's preferences when it comes to sustainability, up-cycled and zero-waste, and see how they liked the dresses made by different draping method. Sustainability is gaining popularity in various areas, including fashion and designing clothes in a sustainable way is crucial because environmental decisions are made during the design stage. While people are begin to understand the significance of sustainability in fashion, there is still a lack of knowledge about how to integrate it into the clothing design process. A study confirmed that understanding sustainability and zero-waste clothing is essential. It also revealed that people's environmental beliefs influence how they view and appreciate zero-waste clothing and sustainable fashion.

Nowadays, the issue of textile waste has become extensive and is greatly affecting the environment. To address this problem, researcher is conducting experiment with waste fabrics to create unique designs through draping. In order to gather waste fabrics, they visit various markets, tailor's shops, boutiques, and fashion houses. By employing zero-waste techniques during the draping process, the researcher created the garment with up-cycled fabrics which is good for the environment.

Fashion plays a significant role in our lives, reflecting our social status and personal style. In today's world, sustainable fashion has become increasingly important. It is a design approach that aims to minimize textile waste and promote the idea of zero waste. Sustainable fashion benefits the environment by using eco-friendly materials, reducing pollution, and supporting the concept of buying fewer items. Zero waste clothing using up-cycled fabrics is a part of this movement, as it reduces textile waste and promotes sustainability.

The design was made using patchwork method, where researcher skillfully stitched together fabric remains to form a unique design. These creations showcase sustainable fashion and creative problem-solving in a short amount of time. Ten experts from fashion field were selected for the evolution for created draped garment. Created garment were shown to the respondents to analyses them visually on the basis of acceptability, marketability, color combination, materials, Designs, techniques, like & dislike. And results reveals that it is liked by all the respondents and made according to the needs of the consumer market and material is also good for environment and used color combination of fabric pieces creates a stunning look to the final design. It is environment friendly which is created by keeping in mind the sustainable environment

Designed Long tail coat by patch work method

Materials:

- waste fabric pieces of different colors
- Muslin fabric for lining
- Pasting for making cuff
- Dress Form for draping

Method:

Firstly, we collected leftover fabric scraps from different tailors' shops, boutiques, and fashion houses. After gathering these pieces, we can choose fabrics that are currently on-trend. Then, we begin by randomly draping these fabric scraps onto a dress form, securing them in place. Once satisfied with the arrangement, we remove the draped fabric and stitch it together to create the garment. Next, we use muslin fabric as a lining to give the garment a polished finish. Taking care of the details, we neatly finish the front part and neckline by adding a black strip. For the sleeves, we stitch together fabric patches to create rectangular pieces. Then, we carefully cut the sleeves and attach them to the bodice.

Process for making garment

Look of Final created Design

Spec Sheet construction details of created garment			
TECHNICAL SHEET			
Style no-	#0001	Date	10-06-2023
Season	Spring season	Size	Medium
Category	Women's wear	Product name	Design-1
Description: Women One Piece long tail coat by creating zero-waste techniques through draping.			
Measurements		Design-1	
Full Length =37			
Across Shoulder = 13.5			
Across Front = 12			
Across Back = 13			
Round Waste = 37			
C to F Waste = 17.5			
Round Bust = 32			
Sleeve Length = 15			
Cuff Length = 6			
Materials			
Waste fabric pieces			
Colours			
Trims		Buttons, Thread, Lining, Pasting	

6. Conclusion

It concludes that draping is a method in which we can do any kind of experiment to create unique designs along with using different materials. As in this research the researcher used up-cycled materials which were left over fabric to create unique design for women. This method is environment friendly as a large amount of waste is coming out from the industries, these fabrics are directly throwing out to the garbage but this method creates stylish designer clothing which is according to the taste of consumer and sustainable also.

Different styles of Garment can be crafted from waste fabric using draping techniques. They are unique, stylish, and eco-friendly. They combine creativity and sustainability, resulting in visually appealing fashion that is friendly for environment.

7. Future Recommendation

- a) A line of clothing can be created by this method
- b) Other methods can be used to create draped designs
- c) Other type of materials can be used for making patch draped garments

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